

DIFFICULTIES IN LISTENING AND UNDERSTANDING SPEECH IN
A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Ominakhan Sheraliyeva

Student of Fergana State University.

Abstract: Interlocutors, according to human habit, take turns to speak and try to understand each other by listening. It is known from life experience that expressing one's opinion orally (speaking) is a type of speech activity that many people like. Various information is obtained by listening to another person. Being in speech communication is a necessary need for a person. In the process of listening, there are cases of partial or complete misunderstanding of the speaker's opinions. The main reason for this is that listening comprehension is not given enough attention.

Key words: Foreign language, listening comprehension, speech activity, academic listening, difficulties.

In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, great importance is attached to teaching listening, because the perception of a foreign language by ear is a complex process that requires maximum attention from the student, and the teacher requires consistent preparation for the development of this type of speech. Therefore, it is necessary to organize the process of listening teaching methodically correctly, that is, the foreign language teaching methodology has the task of properly organizing and planning this process in such a way that the level of formation of students' listening abilities meets the requirements.

Listening and speaking are two sides of a single phenomenon called speaking.

Types of hearing:

Academic listening acts as an educational tool, introduces linguistic material, serves as a way to create strong auditory images of linguistic units, is a necessary condition for mastering oral speech, forming and developing communicative listening skills.

Academic listening allows you to listen to the same material several times (with independent work) and 2 times (with class work, under the guidance of the teacher). Repeated listening provides a more complete and accurate understanding of the audio text, as well as a better recall of its content and linguistic form, especially when the listened text is used for further repetition, oral discussion or written presentation.

Speech Listening - A receptive WFD that focuses on aural perception and understanding of spoken speech in one listen. It is customary to distinguish types of communicative listening in foreign and domestic methods depending on the

communicative situation (educational task) and their connection with expressive oral speech.

In this process, listening comprehension serves as an effective way to remember language material. Teaching listening comprehension is one of the main tasks in the elementary grades of secondary schools. A person usually achieves spiritual maturity through the activities of seeing, hearing (listening) and reading. In psycholinguistics, listening comprehension is defined as the process of decoding information coming through the sound channel. "Listening comprehension is a three-stage activity, behind general auditory perception (acoustic apperception), phonemic differentiation of the sound side of words and understanding of their essence, the content of the speech is perceived, learned and, finally, understood" (J.J. Jalolov). When listening and understanding speech in the native language, the form and content are perceived as a whole, while in English, the combination of the means of expression (language material) and the expressed content (text) is somewhat difficult. In order to improve the content, students need to master the lexical, grammatical and pronunciation skills of the language. Knowledge of lexis and pronunciation in understanding the text is of particular importance in understanding the general content, and mastering grammar in understanding the content with specific details. In short, listening comprehension means hearing or understanding the speaker's speech directly or with the help of technical means. In other words, listening comprehension means perceiving the speech of others (live or mechanically recorded) and understanding its content.

Listening comprehension is a three-stage activity, the content of the speech is perceived, learned and understood behind the general auditory perception (acoustic apperception), distinguishing the sound side of words (phonemics) and understanding the essence. It is known that listening comprehension, which is considered a type and skill of speech activity, is the goal and means of education. At this point, it is necessary to make a distinction between two categories, i.e., on the one hand, understanding through words (relying on the speech experience in the language) and, on the other hand, with the help of things (due to life experience, knowledge of the speech situation). Therefore, the speech, topics and situations recommended at the initial stage of foreign language education are familiar and known to the students, and the language material is completely new and unfamiliar to them. Each type of speech activity has its own difficulties. There are several difficulties in listening comprehension. Knowing them is one of the crucial conditions for teaching a foreign language. The problems of perception, including perceptual understanding of speech, have been developed in great detail in world psychology.

The purpose of recognizing the difficulty a student faces in listening comprehension is to take measures to prevent it. Challenges require work and time, and require special exercises. By eliminating (neutralizing) the difficulties in time, it is possible to speed up the educational process and develop the most acceptable (optimal) methodology of teaching. Difficulties in learning a language or in life in general are determined by cause and effect. Difficulty can be identified in advance, its causes can be known. The emergence of difficulty is determined by the type of errors and the degree of achievement of the intended result. Correct formation of the psychophysiological mechanisms of listening comprehension is of great importance in order to overcome difficulties in the student's ability to perceive the speech of others and understand its content.

References:

1. Великанова А. В. Компетентностно-ориентированный подход к образованию/А.В.Вели-канова//Серия «Компетентностно-ориентированный подход к образованию». – Вып. 2 – Самара : Профи, 2002. – С. 92
2. Bekmurodova.U.B. Abstract on "Using innovative technologies in teaching English", Tashkent 2012.
3. N. Q. Khatamova, M.N. Mirzayeva. "INTERACTIVE METHODS USED IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS" (methodical guide), Navoi, 2006, 40 pages.
4. Joraboyev, B. B. O. (2021). Using authentic materials on english lessons. Academic research in educational sciences, 2